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OP 33**Nurses' and Physicians' Knowledge and Practices on Infection Control in Managing Patients with Temporary Hemodialysis Catheters**

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Background: In nephrology units, infection control (IC) is vital due to the heightened risk for patients with compromised immune systems. Temporary hemodialysis catheters pose infection risks, necessitating stringent preventive measures. Hemodialysis (HD) nurses and physicians play crucial roles in implementing these measures, yet there is evidence of increasing infections among these patients.

Objective: To assess nurses' and physicians' knowledge and practices for controlling infections among patients with temporary hemodialysis catheters

Methods: A descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted in the HD units, Nephrology-wards, and Intensive-care units at the National Hospital with 86 nurses and, 40 physicians. A self-administered questionnaire was distributed to gather information regarding nurses' and physicians' knowledge and practice towards IC among patients on temporary hemodialysis catheters. Data were analyzed to obtain percentages, frequencies, and relationships using SPSS version 17.0.

Results: In total, 126 surveys were completed by nurses (68.3%), and physicians (31.7%). Compared to nurses, physicians had slightly higher mean±SD scores in knowledge (7.47 ± 2.09 vs 7.6 ± 1.68 , $p=0.009$). Of the total, around 35% of nurses and physicians demonstrated good knowledge. The mean±SD score for nurses' practices was 1.40 ± 0.27 , and physicians' scores were higher at 1.55 ± 0.36 . A positive correlation between knowledge and practice was found among nurses ($r=0.52$, $p<0.05$), but not among physicians ($r=-0.16$, $p=0.47$). Practices among nurses was associated with year of experience ($p<0.05$), while physicians' practice and year of experience was not significantly associated ($p=0.696$).

Conclusions: The study on infection control among 126 nephrology unit healthcare professionals in nephrology units found that physicians exhibited slightly higher knowledge scores than nurses. Nurses show a positive correlation between knowledge and practice, influenced by years of experience. Conversely, physicians' practices are not significantly linked to experience. According to study findings, increasing nurses' exposure to nephrology units enhances proficiency, leading to improved patient care outcomes.

Keywords: Hemodialysis, Knowledge, Nephrology nurses, Physicians, Practice,